

Heterocyclic Systems containing Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom. Reactions of *p*-Bis(5-mercapto-4-amino-*s*-triazol-3-yl)- phenylene with Chloroacetaldehyde Diethylacetal, Benzoin, Chloroacetic Acid, Carbon Disulphide and 2,3-Dichloroquinoxaline

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Manuscript received 14 December 1988, accepted 9 March 1989

p-Bis(5-mercapto-4-amino-*s*-triazol-3-yl)phenylene (1) with chloroacetaldehyde diethylacetal, benzoin chloroacetic acid, carbon disulphide and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline furnishes compounds 2-6. The antibacterial, antifungal and diuretic activities of some of the compounds have been evaluated.

IN continuous to our earlier studies on the synthesis of condensed triazole systems¹, we report here the synthesis of some interesting heterocyclic systems derived from *p*-bis(5-mercapto-4-amino-*s*-triazol-3-yl)phenylene (1)² (Scheme 1) and the biological activities associated with them.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) chloroacetaldehyde diethylacetal, (ii) PhCHOHCOPh, KOH, (iii) ClCH₂COOH, NaOAc, (iv) CS₂, pyridine, (v) 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline, NaOAc.

The reaction of 1 with chloroacetaldehyde diethylacetal, chloroacetic acid and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline in absolute ethanol yielded *p*-bis(7*H*-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)phenylene hydrochloride (2), *p*-bis(5*H*-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-6-(7*H*)-one-3-yl)phenylene (4) and *p*-bis(*s*-triazolo[3'

4' : 2,3] [1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxalin-2-yl)phenylene (6) respectively in good yields. However, the treatment of an ethanolic solution of 1 with benzoin in presence of potassium hydroxide and CS₂ in presence of pyridine yielded *p*-bis(5*H*-6,7-diphenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)phenylene (3) and *p*-bis(*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazol-6-(5*H*)-thion-3-yl)phenylene (5) respectively.

The structures of 2-6 are compatible with their elemental analysis and spectral data. The absence of C=O band in compounds 2 and 3 while the appearance of C=O band (1 710 cm⁻¹) in 4 corroborate the cyclic structures in these compounds.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Tlc was performed on silica gel plates using acetone-benzene (1 : 3) as irrigant. Infrared spectra (nujol or KBr) were recorded, on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer.

p-Bis(5-mercapto-4-amino-*s*-triazol-3-yl)phenylene (1): It was prepared from terephthalic acid bishydrazide following the method of Reid and Heindel³, (52%), m.p. 280°d (ethanol) (Found: N, 36.85; S, 20.91. C₁₀H₁₀N₈S₂ requires: N, 36.60; S, 20.92%); ν_{max} 820 (*p*-disubstituted benzene ring), 1 500 (C-N), 1 600 (C=C and C=N), 1 625 (N-H in-plane bending), 2 600 (S-H), 3 020 (C-H aromatic), 3 220, 3 400 cm⁻¹ (N-H, NH₂).

p-Bis(7*H*-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)phenylene hydrochloride (2): A mixture of 1 (1.53 g,

0.005 mol), chloroacetaldehyde diethylacetal (1.53 g, 0.01 mol), concentrated HCl (1–2 drops) and isopropanol (100 ml) was refluxed for about 6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the resulting white solid was washed several times with hot ethanol, yield (1.4 g, 66%), m.p. > 290° (Found: C, 38.93; H, 3.28; N, 26.20; S, 14.81. $C_{14}H_{12}N_2S_2$ requires: C, 39.34, H, 2.81; N, 26.23; S, 14.99%); ν_{max} 840 (*p*-disubstituted benzene), 1525 (C–N), 1600, 1650 (C=C and C=N), 3030 (C–H aromatic) and 3400 cm^{-1} (NH).

p-Bis(5H-6,7-diphenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-3-yl)phenylene (3): A mixture of 1 (1.53 g, 0.005 mol) and benzoin (2.12 g, 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (150 ml) was heated to get a clear solution and then added to a hot solution (2*N*) of KOH (2.0 ml) and refluxed for about 2 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give yellow crystals, (0.9 g, 28%), m.p. 242° (Found: C, 69.57; H, 4.22; N, 17.57; S, 9.48. $C_{38}H_{28}N_8S_2$ requires: C, 69.30; H, 3.45; N, 17.02; S, 9.73%); ν_{max} 695, 760 (mono-substituted benzene) 840 (*p*-disubstituted benzene), 1500, 1550 (C–N), 1610 (C=C and C=N) and 3200–3300 cm^{-1} (NH).

p-Bis(5H-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-6(7H)-one-3-yl)phenylene (4): A mixture of 1 (1.53 g, 0.005 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.95 g, 0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (150 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (1.50 g, 77%), m.p. 220°d (Found: C, 44.08; H, 3.12; N, 29.64; S, 17.28. $C_{14}H_{10}N_8S_2O_2$ requires: C, 43.52; H, 2.59; N, 29.02; S, 16.58%); ν_{max} 842 (*p*-disubstituted benzene ring), 1525 (C–N), 1595 (C=C and C=N) 1710 (C=O) and 3150 cm^{-1} (NH).

p-Bis(*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazol-6-(5H-thion-3-yl)phenylene (5): A solution of 1 (1.3 g, 0.005 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was treated with CS_2 (1 ml) dropwise with stirring at the room temperature. After the addition was complete, the mixture was heated with continuous stirring, in an oil-bath at 100° for 6 h. Then pyridine was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in a small quantity of benzene, diluted with ether, charcolised, filtered, concentrated and treated with hexane to give light brown coloured crystals, (1.1 g, 56%), m.p. > 270° (Found: C, 37.45; H, 2.08; N, 29.27; S, 33.49. $C_{12}H_8N_8S_4$ requires: C, 36.92; H, 1.54; N, 28.72; S, 32.82%); ν_{max} 840 (*p*-disubstituted benzene ring), 1160 (C=S), 1500 (C–N), 1625 (C=C and C=N) and 3110 cm^{-1} (NH).

p-Bis(*s*-triazolo[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxalin-2-yl)phenylene (6): A mixture of 1 (1.53 g, 0.005 mol), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1.99 g, 0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (1.64 g, 0.02 mol) in

absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol giving yellow granular product, (1.9 g, 68%), m.p. 232°d (Found: C, 55.3; H, 2.89; N, 29.72; S, 11.99. $C_{26}H_{14}N_{12}S_2$ requires: C, 55.91; H, 2.51; N, 30.11; S, 11.47%); ν_{max} 843 (*p*-disubstituted benzene), 1515 (C–N), 1600 (C=C and C=N) and 3350 cm^{-1} (NH).

Antimicrobial activities :

Biological activities : The compounds 4–6 were studied for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*), gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and fungus (*Candida albicans*) using neat samples and serial plate dilution method³. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values for 4 and 5 against *C. albicans* were found to be 250 and 125 $\mu g\ ml^{-1}$ respectively. Compounds 4 and 5 showed activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* when treated as neat sample.

Burn's method⁴, as recorded by Heller⁵, was used for diuretic testing in rats. Albino rats of both sexes (150–200 g) were fasted overnight but allowed water *ad libitum* in order to determine the diuretic activity. Groups of eight rats were used. Test compounds were administered in volumes of 10% alcohol load which amounted to 5% of the body weight of rats. The control group was given the solvent only. Four rats were placed together in the metabolic cages resting on a glass funnel. Cross-over tests were performed after 48 h. Urine volume was measured every 30 min for 5 h. The diuresis was calculated by comparing the urine volumes of control and experimental groups. The compounds 4 and 5 were tested for diuretic activity against the dose 50 mg, 100 mg and 1 gm/kg and found to possess no appreciable diuretic activity at these concentrations.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C S I R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them G.S.R.A.) and to Head of the Chemistry Department, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak for facilities.

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